

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Ismaylova U

EXPRESSION OF EDUCATIONAL IDEAS IN KARAKALPAK TOLGAWS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
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2023/YANVAR

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HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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